

CORRUPTION AND MILITARY EXPENDITURE IN NIGERIA

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Keywords

Military Expenditure, Corruption, Financial Probity, Good Governance, Macro-economic Environment, Neo-patrimonial Theory

Abstract: *The effect of corruption on military expenditure inter-alia include diversion of developmental funds, increased spate of insecurity which is well established in extant literatures; however, empirical evidence are quite few; hence this study was undertaken to establish the empirical relationship between military expenditure and corruption. To carry out this study, secondary data were sourced from The World Development Indicators (2023) of the World Bank. The study adopted ex-post research design in line with theoretical underpinning of Neo-patrimonial theory to test the hypotheses that there is no significant impact of corruption on military expenditure in Nigeria. The dependent variable for the study was military expenditure; while financial probity, good governance, corruption control, and macro-economic environment were used as the explanatory variables. The ARDL model was used as the estimation technique. From the analyses of data, it was discovered that corruption control, financial probity and good governance had significant effect on military expenditure in the long run. The Test for causality showed no direct causality between corruption and military expenditure at 5% level of significance. The post-estimation results showed there was no significant violation of econometric assumptions. Based on the findings, it was recommended that concerted efforts should be made by the government to curtail corrupt practices in governance; the government should ensure probity in the use and management of its appropriation budget so as to ensure maximum compliance with its provision and follow due process in any procurement policy that enhances transparency and accountability; and Lastly, the government should enshrine and imbibe the tenets of good governance as it will produce a positive spill-over effect on budget management and impact on the economic environment in the long run.*

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

The recent insecurity disturbances, especially internal insecurity; is not a problem that is unique to Nigeria: the US, UK and many countries, face the challenges of insecurity within their borders on a daily basis. The difference between them and Nigeria's is how the threats are being; how knowledgeable and prepared they are; how they deploy resources against the threats; how effective they are; how patriotic and united these people are against threats of insecurity (ACLED, 2023). In recent times, Nigeria suddenly metamorphosed into an abode of serial bombing, hostage taking, armed robbery, cold-blooded killings, kidnapping and ethno-religious conflicts traceable to militant groups and terrorists with conflicting ideological, political and religious agenda. This recent events over the years has made the country to resort to military spending to arrest these insurgent attacks and rising security threats in the country. This spending on the military was made possible by direct budgeting of huge amount of funds for the purpose of security amidst the economic situation of the country. However, despite the resources and amount spent to combat insecurity, the results have been a shortfall from expectations. One factor responsible for this is the level of corruption that permeates

every facet of the economy. In other words, corruption has been able to permeate the defense sector and eroded the gains from military spending as a result. Thus, corruption has been particularly destructive in the defense and security sector. With lower oil prices, corrupt elites have increasingly exploited alternative illicit revenue streams. The secret nature of defense and security budgets has made them the easiest and most lucrative opportunity to exploit. While Boko Haram has constructed a conflict economy geared around pillage, racketeering, kidnapping, senior Nigerian security players have also profited from the insurgency. Extra-budgetary spending on counterterrorism has dramatically increased over the last decade; especially between 2014 and 2015, 2018 and 2021 and with it, the scale and scope of corrupt opportunities in the defence sector. Analyzing the trend of Nigeria's total expenditure on security in recent years shows that about \$2.36b, \$2.07b, \$1.72b, \$1.62b, \$2.04b, \$1.86b, \$2.57b, \$4.47b, \$3.11b had been spent in 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021 and 2022 respectively (CBN, 2022; Federal Government Budgets, 2014-2022). Despite, huge resources been sunk in total security spending, yet the activities of insurgents are still rampant and prevailing in the country. Corruption has succeeded in whittling down the effectiveness of the Nigerian

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Army, the largest in West Africa and the integrity of the country's navy has been compromised. This has resulted to a corrupt war economy which has constituted an incentive to high ranking of officials and security personnel who crave to perpetuate insurgency for personal gains. The extent to which these corrupt practices have elongated the military campaign over a longer period is the subject matter of this study.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The poor state of security in Nigeria through the perpetration of crises and corrupt-handling or theft of military appropriations meant for procuring the necessary equipment to confront and suppress insurgency, have been pointing to the systemic failures and frustrations which the Nigerian military suffers in its effort to attain the demands of national security. Despite joining other nations that prioritize national security; Nigeria has spent a good chunk of their budgetary allocation on security due to the activities of Herdsmen and Boko-Haram militants. Analyzing the trend of Nigeria's total security expenditure in recent years showed that about \$2.36b, \$2.07b, \$1.72b, \$1.62b, \$2.04b, \$1.86b, \$2.57b, \$4.47b, \$3.11b had been spent in 2006, 2007, 2008, 2009, 2010, 2011, 2012, 2013 and 2014 respectively. However, despite the rising increases in total security spending, it is rather doubtful whether it has translated to the meaningful progress as

a result some bottlenecks such as corrupt practices among military officers and contractors in charge of procurement process of military hardwares, on one hand, poor management of the budget and lack of quality leadership in terms of governance. These factors put together have not helped the country record significant results in the fight against insurgency over the past decade. There seems to be the trend of profiteering from the insurgency crises and this has led to questions about the efficacy of the government in combating insecurity in the country with transparent approach to it. Hence, the pertinent questions worth asking remain as follows: What are the effects of corruption on administration of military spending in Nigeria? and does it have any long run correlation with financial probity on the part of the government, good governance and the macro-economic environment at large?

1.3. Objectives of the Study.

The specific objective of this study are as follows:

- i. To ascertain the extent to which corruption affects military expenditure in Nigeria;
- iii. To find out the extent to which financial probity affects military expenditure in Nigeria;
- iii. To find out the extent to which the macro-economic environment affects military expenditure in Nigeria; and lastly

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iv. To investigate the relationship between good governance and military expenditure in Nigeria.

1.4. Research Questions.

The specific questions that will guide this study are as follows:

- i. To what extent has corruption affected the military expenditure of Nigeria?
- ii. How has financial probity affected the military expenditure of Nigeria?
- iii. To what extent does the macro-economic environment affect military expenditure of Nigeria?
- iv. Is there any impact of good governance on military expenditure of Nigeria?

1.5 Research Hypotheses.

The following research hypotheses will guide this study:

- i. Ho: There is no significant relationship between corruption and military expenditure in Nigeria;
- ii. Ho: There is no significant relationship between financial probity and military expenditure in Nigeria;
- iii. Ho: There is no significant relationship between the macro-economic environment and military expenditure of Nigeria;
- iv. Ho: There is no significant relationship between good governance and military expenditure of Nigeria.

1.6 Scope of the Study

The study is centered on corruption and military expenditure in Nigeria. It is based on secondary data with a time period of 34 years i.e.1990-2023. The time series period chosen for this study was adduced to adequately capture military spending in the military and civilian administrations in Nigeria. This is because the time periods sufficiently reflect the gamut of experience Nigeria has had with military operations. The ambit of this study is within quantitative analysis and thus, focuses on five key variables being corruption, good governance, financial probity and macro-economic environment which aid model formulation for econometric measurement and analysis of short run and long run effects.

1.7 Significance of the Study

The study will be of immense benefit to policy makers and institutions as it seeks to establish the theoretical connection between corruption and military expenditure in Nigeria with the aid of the Neo-patrimonial theory. Furthermore, it will present an opportunity to empirically assess other literatures on corruption and military expenditure in Nigeria. This will bring forth the empirical underpinning of each study and how it connects with the scope of the study; for instance, it will examine the empirical links between the study and the selected variables such as corruption, good governance, financial probity and the macro-economic environment; and their link with military spending. Previous

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studies will form the bedrock for model formulation and estimation that will aid in lending empirical evidence to the topic. In addition, it will be of immense enlightenment to researchers as it would broaden the view of the research subject by opening it up for criticism and further researches through identified gaps in the literature.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Military expenditure and corruption

According to Wikipedia, military expenditure is the amount of financial resources dedicated by to raising and maintaining an armed forces or other methods essential for defense purposes. This defense budget is often used interchangeably as Military budget, often reflects how strongly a country perceives the likelihood of threats against it, or the amount of aggression it wishes to conjure; hence, commits resources to maintain its internal and external peace and stability. Thus, Adejoh & Ukhammi (2022) views military spending as a measure that gives a clear picture of the part of a country's resources that it would spend on its armed forces. The size of a budget reflects the country's ability to fund military activities. Factors that determine a defense budget include the size of that country's economy, other financial demands on that entity, and the

willingness of that entity's government or people to fund such military activity.

The broadest definition of military expenditure is that of the UN definition. The UN definition is based on Stockholm International Peace Research Institute (SIPRI) definition. In the view of SIPRI (2010), defence expenditures include all current and capital expenditures on the armed forces, including peace keeping forces; defence ministries and other governmental agencies engaged in defence projects; paramilitary forces when judged to be trained, equipped and available for military operations, and military space activities. Such expenditures should include: personnel-all expenditures on current personnel, military and civil retirements, pensions of military personnel and social services for personnel and their families; operations and maintenance; procurement; military research and development; military construction; and military aid (in the military expenditures of the donor country).

Corruption on the other hand is a pervasive issue that significantly erodes governance structures, undermines institutional capacities, and exacerbates socioeconomic inequalities. These systemic vulnerabilities frequently catalyze violent conflicts, particularly in fragile states or those endowed with abundant natural resources (Le Billon, 2001). The detrimental effects of corruption are especially pronounced

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in the defense sector, where it undermines military operational efficiency, siphons critical resources away from their intended purposes, and fosters a culture of impunity. Such dynamics are highlighted by Raballand & Recanatini (2023), who argue that corruption is both a symptom and a driver of state fragility, ultimately undermining the prospects for sustainable peace and long-term stability.

Additionally, Joly (2021) emphasizes that corruption, conflict, and instability are deeply intertwined, with corruption often serving as one of the primary root causes of conflict on a global scale. According to her analysis, corruption cripples national institutions by limiting their capacity to address citizens' needs and stoking grievances that can escalate into widespread unrest. Insurgent groups frequently exploit these grievances and leverage disillusionment and disenfranchisement to bolster their ranks and expand their influence (Mauro, 2017).

In Nigeria, the dual impact of corruption is particularly stark. On one hand, it debilitates the state's ability to address the underlying causes of insurgency; on the other, it provides insurgents with potent propaganda tools to delegitimize the Government. Boko Haram, for example, has successfully exploited local frustrations stemming from ineffective governance and perceived exploitation by elites. This exploitation is amplified by corruption

within the systems responsible for counterinsurgency financing, where critical funds are often mismanaged or embezzled (Arowolo, 2022). The group's ability to tap into such grievances has not only prolonged the insurgency but also further entrenched insecurity and instability across the region.

The resulting inefficiency prolongs the conflict and erodes public trust in the state's ability to maintain peace and stability. Aldieri (2023) further notes that such governance failures undermine the state's legitimacy, making it increasingly difficult to implement effective conflict-resolution measures.

The "resource curse" phenomenon further compounds the corruption-conflict nexus in resource-rich countries like Nigeria. Despite the country's substantial oil revenues, corruption has siphoned these funds away from developmental priorities, redirecting them into private hands and fueling economic disparities (Ross, 2004). Although defense budgets have increased significantly in recent years, the persistence of insurgent activities underscores the inefficiency and mismanagement rooted in corruption. This paradox highlights the need for systemic reform within Nigeria's governance and defense structures.

2.1.2 An overview of corruption and military expenditure in Nigeria

Here we make references to some past events concerning military expenditure where

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corruption took place and these are examined as follows:

i. Boat supply saga

Premium Times reported that sometime in 2008, Amit Sade, an Israeli contractor, was awarded combined contracts worth over \$3m (Ogala, 2018). According to the report, he was first asked to deliver 'assorted ammunitions' at \$2 million. In addition, he was also asked to supply 20 units of K-38 twin-hull boats at the cost of \$5 million each. Even though he was given a 95% upfront payment to provide the ammunition against the standard practice in contract award, according to the investigation, he delivered 63% of the contract (Ogala, 2018). Similarly, on K38 boats, he was paid 80% upfront but offered a job of only 40%. According to the investigation, Mr. Sade's records showed he was awarded six other military contracts worth \$4 million. Records also indicated that he had failed to deliver them. According to the investigations carried out by multiple sources, and which were supported by the investigation carried out by Transparency International (TI), Nigeria lost a whopping \$15 billion in 20 years in the defense sector through arms deals, which also coincided with the period Boko Haram began its armed campaign (Odunsi, 2017; Ogala, 2018; Sahara Reporters, 2022; TI, 2017; Yakubu & Falode, 2021). Former Nigeria Vice President, Yemi Osinbajo, corroborated the massive, pervasive corruption

in the defense sector when he alleged that \$15bn defense contract was missing and could not be accounted for and that two weeks before the election, 100bn naira (\$50m) and \$295m were used for the re-election bid of the then sitting President under cover of security (Arowolo, 2022; Osinbajo, 2017).

ii. Progress Limited gift

Between 2006 and 2010, Nigeria's Ministry of Defence awarded two contracts to Progress Limited. According to the contract details, 42 BRTR-3U armored personnel carriers and spare parts were to be supplied to the Nigerian army. There was no evidence of documented contracts or agreements. The contract seemed to be awarded at a rendezvous without signing any contract agreement between the parties. There was no market survey to reflect the market value of the carriers; out of the required 42 units, 26 units of used armored personnel carriers were supplied, which broke down two years after during its deployment for a peacekeeping operation in Sudan (Ogala, 2018; Sahara Reporters, 2022; Yakubu & Falode, 2021). According to Sahara Reporters (2022), this was a perversion of due process and abuse of office to satisfy a predetermined end of some self-serving top military brass.

iii. The Shaldag contracts

This particular shady contract, codenamed "The Shaldag Contract", was a ship supply contract that had mainly remained phony

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(Ogala, 2018; Sahara Reporters, 2022). According to the report, the contract betrayed every sense of decorum and patriotism. Transparency International (2017) reports that some few military generals, in connivance with Shaldag, threw caution to the wind and defiled due process in awarding contracts to satisfy their insatiable quest for primitive capital accumulation. The contract deal was about a supply of two fast assault boats, each with a market value of about \$5 million. However, these two boats were supplied at the rate of \$25 million. It was reported that Nigeria lost a whopping \$15 million in the deal. It was not clear how the excess money was shared among the conspirators, but what was however clear was the arrest of the middleman, Amit Sade, who was alleged to have received \$1.47 million in brokerage fees (Ogala, 2018; Sahara Reporters, 2021; TI, 2017).

iv. Cash for black market arms in South Africa

In 2014, \$9.3 million in cash was confiscated from two Nigerians and an Israeli by South Africa border authorities. A private jet owned by a renowned Nigerian pastor was used to ferry the money. The money, stashed in three trunks, was discovered by airport scanners officers (Ogala, 2018). This incident nearly caused a diplomatic row between the South African Government and its Nigeria counterpart after the former rebuffed every

entreaty made by the latter for the release of the fund. Customs officers discovered the money hoarded in three suitcases after the bags containing the money were put through airport scanners. Following the confession of the Nigerian Government that the money was meant to procure arms in the black market for the prosecution of the Boko Haram insurgency in Northeastern Nigeria, the South African authorities were somewhat adamant that the hard currency breached every known international pact and money laundry act (Sahara Reporters, 2021; TI, 2017). After its release to the Nigerian Government, how the money was later spent remained a mystery, as there was no record of arms purchases with the funds.

v. NIA Ikoyigate

Another flurry of illicit cash discovery was codenamed Ikoyigate in 2017 (Arowolo, 2022). The cash stockpiled in hard currencies of \$43m, £27, 000 and N23m (\$15m) was hidden in a vulgar but well-furnished house at Ikoyi, Lagos (Arowolo, 2022; Bulusson, 2017; Gabriel, 2017). The National Intelligent Agency (NIA) Director later claimed the money was meant for undisclosed exceptional security and defense projects. A whistleblower who discovered the money was awarded some unspecified amount in line with the newly introduced whistleblower policy. The entitlement ranged between 2.5 percent and 5 percent of the amount recovered

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if they provided the Government with information that directly led to the recovery of stolen or concealed public funds or assets, provided the Government did not already have the information, and it could not have obtained it from any other publicly available source (Arowolo, 2022). The whistleblower would only get rewarded if the money was recovered because of the information they supplied (Arowolo, 2022).

As had been earlier established in the previous section, the procurement process in Nigeria's defense sector was fraught with irregularities. Corruption in the defense sector slows down the efforts of men and officers of the armed forces on the battlefield, prolonging the fight against insurgency. Abolurin (2012) and Jimoh, Olaniyi & Abdulsalami (2017), substantiated this when they submitted that corruption has waned the fight against insurgency and escalated the war. According to them, the corrupt ruling elite and top military brass alike have benefitted from the conflict in the northeast to the very detriment of the peace of Nigeria.

According to the investigation by Transparency International (TI), reported by Daily Trust, Premium Times and Sahara Reporters, \$15 billion was meant for the supply of arms, training of military personnel, allowance of military personnel and food supply in the fight against Boko Haram insurgency had been

stolen over some time, leaving the military without cognate arms and ammunition, equipment and needed morale to diligently prosecute the war (Odunsi, 2017; Ogala, 2018; Sahara Reporters, 2022; TI, 2017). Also, a presidential inquiry set up in 2016 indicted the top military brass and their civilian collaborators. It was revealed that fake contracts worth over \$2bn were awarded between 2011 and 2015. These funds were meant to procure ammunition to fight the Boko Haram insurgency (Aljazeera, 2015; BBC News, 2015). Individuals and corporate organizations have also been fingered in the utter diversion or thievery of funds meant to purchase arms and ammunition to prosecute the fight against insurgency in Nigeria (Alemika, 2012; Aljazeera, 2015; BBC News, 2015; Ogala, 2018; TI, 2017). These irregularities in the procurement process have grave ramifications for the fight against insurgency. Apart from slowing down the war, they could have implications for the morale of the combatant, depleting their sense of patriotism and commitment to the national cause (Abba, 2023; Abubakar, 2023; Maina, 2021).

2.2 Theoretical review: The Neopatrimonial theory

This theoretical framework provides a powerful lens for understanding Nigeria's deeply entrenched relationship between corruption and counterinsurgency financing. This

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theoretical framework is rooted in Weber's (1968) concept of patrimonialism, which describes a system where governance and leadership rely on personal loyalty and hierarchical patronage rather than institutionalized rules. Neo-patrimonialism expands on this by reflecting the fusion of public and private spheres within governance systems, where state resources are often privatized for the personal benefit of ruling elites (Eisenstadt, 1973; Bratton & van de Walle, 1999). This approach underscores systemic practices such as clientelism, nepotism, and resource misappropriation, particularly prevalent in many African states, including Nigeria (Anders, 2005; Olaniyan, 2015). In the Nigerian context, neo-patrimonialism manifests in the weakening of formal state institutions due to their overlap with informal networks of patronage. These networks often operate to benefit a few at the expense of the broader population, promoting corruption and mediocrity while eroding meritocracy and institutional efficiency (Nkwede, 2015). Thus, from the foregoing, one can see that this theory is apt for this study as it explains the nexus between the blending of formal and informal governance as it undermines accountability and transparency, creating an environment conducive to the mismanagement of public resources. Neo-patrimonialism thus serves as a crucial framework for examining how

governance failures, especially those rooted in corruption and resource mismanagement, have exacerbated the escalation insecurity in Nigeria.

2.3 Empirical Review

There are few literatures on the nexus between corruption and military expenditure that are empirically based; however, some of them are examined in details as follows:

Shimawua (2020) assessed the military campaign against Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria. This study examined the extent to which corruption has affected military operations in the fight. Data was obtained from secondary materials which include books, journals, periodicals, newspapers, and the internet. Data analysis was done using the technique of content analysis. Findings revealed that the fight against Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria has lasted so long due to corruption that has eaten deep into the fabrics of the military hierarchy, and that this has significantly affected the fortunes of the military in the Boko Haram fight.

Duruji (2018), examined the military's budget against the Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria covering the period of 2009-2017. The study found that there were shortfalls with respect to monies budgeted for the war and what has been achieved so far, stating that the expenditures were not commensurate to what has been

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achieved in the war, thus advocating for prudence in managing military budget against insurgency in the country.

Usman (2017), assessed the impact of corruption in the military's fight against insurgency in the north eastern region of Nigeria covering 2009-2015. The study employed secondary data and adopted content and observational method of analysis. It discovered that the failure of the Nigerian military to defeat insurgents in the country was due to corruption perpetrated by highly placed government functionaries, thus advocating for the continued war against corruption.

Akume & Godswill (2016) analyzed the challenge of managing insurgency in Nigeria spanning 2009 to 2015. The study used documentary research method to examine why government is unable to contain the menace of insurgency. The paper discovered that government agencies' opportunistic behavior accounts for the poor performance of government in wiping out insurgency. The study pointed at large scale corruption as the reason for the poor performance of Nigeria's military forces.

Suleiman & Aminu (2015), in their study examined how the cycle of bad governance and corruption have affected the fight against the Boko Haram insurgents in Nigeria. The study examined the cycle of bad governance and corruption particularly in military expenditure

in Nigeria's north-east fight against the insurgents. Qualitative data were employed through interviews. The study found that the war has not been fairly fought, concluding that corruption has affected the successes of the Nigerian forces, thereby prolonging the military's campaign against the insurgency.

2.9 Gap in the Study

There exists few empirical literature on corruption and military expenditure in Nigeria. Furthermore, most of the studies were carried out using descriptive analysis, (Akume and Godswill (2016); Shimawua (2020); with recourse to few studies like Suleiman and Aminu (2015) that were quantitatively analyzed. The empirical works reviewed above were mostly qualitative in analysis; however, this study models military expenditure as a function of corruption and other control variables such as budgetary financial management, quality of public administration and macro-economic environment. These variables thereby close the gap in previous studies and using a time period of 1990-2023 brings the study to a more recent period to make room for lending empirical evidence to support or refute the impact of corruption on military expenditure in Nigeria.

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This research study utilized Ex-post facto research design to investigate "The effect of corruption on military expenditure in Nigeria:

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(1990-2023)". Ex-post facto is a research after the facto has been known and it applies to secondary data (Anyanwu, 2000). Based on the nature of this research study, secondary data was employed.

3.2 Source of Data

The data for this study was obtained from the World Development Indicators of World Bank (2023).

3.3. Model Specification

In an attempt to investigate the "Impact of government debt stock on economic growth of the Nigerian economy: (1983-2023)", the work of Suleiman and Aminu (2015), on "bad governance and corruption in the fight against the Boko Haram insurgents in Nigeria" was reviewed. The study employed secondary data and adopted content and observational method of analysis. It discovered that the failure of the Nigerian military to defeat insurgents in the country was due to corruption perpetrated by highly placed government functionaries, thus advocating for the continued war against corruption. However, this study makes an improvement over their analysis by modelling military expenditure as a function of corruption as shown in the model below:

MILEXP-f (CCTL, QUAPUB, BFMGT, MAECON)

In econometric form:

MILEXP=bo+b1CCTL+b2QUAPUB+b3BFMGT+b4MAECON+ μ

Thus; the model variables are defined as follows:

MILEXP= military expenditure.

CCTL= Corruption control.

QUAPUB-quality of public administration as a proxy for good governance.

MAECON-macro-economic environment.

BFMGT-budgetary financial management index as a proxy for financial probity.

b-b4 are coefficients of parameters estimates and bo is the intercept of the model. μ is the white noise error term. It is expected that $b_1 < 0$, $b_2 > 0$, $b_3 > 0$ and $b_4 > 0$ as our a priori expectations.

3.4. Pre-Estimation Tests

3.4.1 Unit Root Test

This was to test for the stationarity of the time series data. Test for stationarity was done to avoid the problem of spurious regression. The Dickey-fuller test statistic was in this regard. The Dickey-fuller

(ADF) statistic when compared with the DF critical value at 5% level of significance and found to be greater in absolute value, we rejected the null hypothesis that a unit does exist, otherwise, we accepted it. The unit root test played an important role in data analysis because it determined the method of estimation of the parameter estimates to be employed.

Decision rule: Accept the null hypothesis if the Prob. F-test and log likelihood ratio exceed the 5% critical value, except otherwise.

Igwemma Andrew A., Emerenini Fabian M., *Ogu Callistus., and Mbata Michael N.

3.4.2 Cointegration Test

The ARDL form for cointegration (Bounds test) states that if F-statistics is greater than $I(0)$ and $I(1)$ bounds, it means there is evidence of long run relationship in the model.

To perform the ARDL Bounds test, 5 cointegration tests are carried out and the hypotheses are stated as follows:

$H_0: \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = \beta_4 = \beta_5 = 0$

$H_1: \beta_1 \neq \beta_2 \neq \beta_3 \neq \beta_4 \neq \beta_5 = 0$

If there is no evidence of cointegration, the error correction model (ECM) representation of the model will be estimated.

3.4.3 Normality Test

This was used to test whether the error terms were normally distributed. The normality test adopted for this study was the Jargue-Bera (JB) statistics which follows a chi-square distribution. If the prob. value of Jargue-Bera (JB) is less 5% level of significance, then the error term is not normally, but if otherwise, we accept the normality assumption.

3.5 Method of Data Analysis

The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) was used for the model estimation.

3.6 Test of Significance

This was to test whether the variables were significant at 5% level of significance individually and jointly. To do this, the t-test was employed to test each of the variables. Stating in terms of null and alternative hypothesis we had:

$H_0: \beta_i = 0$, where $i = 1-4$ and

$H_1: \beta_i \neq 0$

Decision rule: Accept H_0 if t stat at $\alpha = 0.05$ otherwise reject H_0 . Alternatively, accept H_0 if $\text{prob.value} > 0.05$, otherwise, reject H_0 . On the other hand, the joint test hypothesis is stated as follows:

$H_0: \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = \beta_4 = 0$; and

$H_1: \beta_1 \neq \beta_2 \neq \beta_3 \neq \beta_4 \neq 0$

Decision rule: Accept H_0 if $\text{prob. value} > 0.05$, otherwise reject H_0 .

3.7 Post-Estimation Test

3.7.1 Test for Autocorrelation

The classical assumption has it that the error terms of observations do not correlate is the error term of one observation does not influence another. To detect this malady, the Breusch-Godfrey test was used.

Decision rule: Accept H_0 if $\text{prob. value} > 0.05$, otherwise reject H_0 .

3.7.2 Test for Heteroscedasticity

The classical assumption has it that the error terms of observations have constant variance; otherwise, non-constant variance and this could create problems in the model estimation which is undesirable and violates the classical assumption of constant variance. To detect this malady, the researcher employed the Breusch-Godfrey-Pagan heteroscedasticity test which follows a chi-square distribution.

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Decision rule: If chi-square F-prob.value > 0.05, it means that there is no serial correlation in the model, except otherwise.

3.7.3 Goodness of Fit of the Model

The adjusted R-squared was examined to test for the Goodness of fit of the model. It explains

Table 4.1: Military expenditure (MILEXP), Budgetary financial management (BFMGT), Quality of public administration (QUAPUB), Corruption control (CCTL) and Macro-economic environment (MAECON) from 1990-2023.

how much variation in the model was accounted for by the explanatory variables of the model. A value above from 50% and above shows a good fit of the model; except below.

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 Data Presentation

YEAR	QUAPUB	BFMGT	MILEXP	CCTL	MAECON
1990	0	0	0.8	0	0
1991	0	0	0.8	0	0
1992	0	0	0.6	0	0
1993	0	0	0.9	0	0
1994	0	0	0.8	0	0
1995	0	0	0.5	0	0
1996	0	0	0.4	0	0
1997	0	0	0.4	0	0
1998	0	0	0.5	0	0
1999	0	0	0.9	0	0
2000	0	0	0.5	0	0
2001	0	0	0.8	0	0
2002	0	0	1	0	0
2003	0	0	0.6	0	0
2004	0	0	0.5	0	0
2005	2.5	3	0.4	3	4.33
2006	2.5	3	0.3	3	4.33
2007	3	3	0.4	3	4.33
2008	3	3	0.5	3	4.3
2009	3	3	0.5	3	4.33

Igwemma Andrew A., Emerenini Fabian M., *Ogu Callistus., and Mbata Michael N.

2010	3	3	0.5	3	4.17
2011	3	3	0.6	3	4
2012	3	3	0.5	3	4.33
2013	2.5	3	0.5	3	4.5
2014	2.5	3	0.4	3	4.33
2015	2.5	3	0.4	3	3.83
2016	2.5	3	0.4	3	3.5
2017	2.5	3	0.4	3	3.33
2018	2.5	3	0.5	3	3.33
2019	2.5	3	0.5	3	3.33
2020	2.5	3	0.6	3	3.5
2021	2.5	3	1	3	3.5
2022	2.5	3	0.7	3	3.5
2023	2.5	3	0.8	3	3.5

Source: CBN Statistical Bulletin (2022) and World Bank Development Indicator (2023)

4.2 Data Analysis and Interpretation

4.2.1 Pre-Estimation Test: Unit Root, Specification Error Test, Cointegration and Normality Test.

4.2.1 Test for Unit Root

The test for unit root was carried with the Augmented Dickey fuller test. The null

hypothesis states that there is presence of Unit root, under the decision rule: if the absolute value of the DF test is greater than that of the critical value, accept the null hypothesis except otherwise.

Table 4.2.1: Unit Root Test Summary: Augmented Dickey-Fuller test.

VARIABLE	ADF (LEVEL)	5% CRITICAL	ADF(1 ST (DIFF))	5% (CRITICAL	REMARK
MILEXP	-3.296350	-2.954021	7.343417*	-2.9571110	I(0)
LNQUAPUB	-1.119951	-2.954021	-5.63069*	-2.9571110	I(1)
LNCCTL	-0.980574	-2.954021	-5.654563	-2.9571110	I(1)
LNMAECON	-1.231448	-2.954021	-5.55626*	-2.9571110	I(1)
LNBFGMT	-233908*	-2.954021	-5.521939*	-2.9571110	I(1)

The Asterisks (*) is used to indicate stationary at the 5% level of significance.

Source: Author’s computation with E-views 9 package.

The unit root test above revealed that MILEXP was found to be stationary at level 1(0), while,

CCTL, QUAPUB, MAECON and BFGMT were stationary at first difference, i.e I (1), which

Igwemma Andrew A., Emerenini Fabian M., *Ogu Callistus., and Mbata Michael N.

implies that the variables have a mixed order of integration; therefore apt for the application of

4.2.1 Cointegration Test: ARDL Bounds Test

H1: There is a long run relationship in the model.

H1: There is a long run relationship in the model.

an ARDL test in analyzing the short run and the long run relationship in the model.

ARDL Bounds Test

Date: 09/22/25 Time: 03:28

Sample: 1997 2023.

Included observations: 27

Null Hypothesis: No long-run relationships exist

Test Statistic	Value	k
F-statistic	8.333493	4
Critical Value Bounds		
Significance	10 Bound	11 Bound
10%	2.45	3.52
5%	2.86	4.01
2.5%	3.25	4.49
1%	3.74	5.06

Source: Author's Computation with E-views 9

From table 4.3 above, the F-statistics for the model is 8.333493 and is greater than the upper I (0) and I (1) bounds of 2.86 and 4.01 respectively at 5% level of significance. Thus, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is presence of cointegration in the model. This implies that there is a long run relationship between corruption and military expenditure in Nigeria. Since there is a long run relationship, we therefore estimate the short run and long run ARDL regression models.

4.2 Model Estimation.

Table 4.3.1: ARDL Output.

Dependent Variable: MILEXP

Method: ARDL

Date: 09/23/25 Time: 05:22

Sample (adjusted): 1997 2023

Included observations: 27 after adjustments

Maximum dependent lags: 7 (Automatic selection)

Model selection method: Akaike info criterion (AIC)

Dynamic regressors (3 lags, automatic):

LNQUAPUB LNMAECON LNCCTL

LNBFMGT

Igwemma Andrew A., Emerenini Fabian M., *Ogu Callistus., and Mbata Michael N.

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Fixed regressors: C

Selected Model: ARDL (7, 3, 2, 3, 2)

Number of models evaluated: 1792

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
MILEXP (-1)	-0.714993	0.234969	-3.042923	0.0287
MILEXP (-2)	-0.711609	0.207901	-3.422825	0.0188
MILEXP (-3)	-0.498787	0.236571	-2.108401	0.0888
MILEXP (-4)	-0.650604	0.184305	-3.530048	0.0167
MILEXP (-5)	-0.725421	0.238420	-3.042623	0.0287
MILEXP (-6)	-0.638185	0.262725	-2.429102	0.0594
MILEXP (-7)	-0.945159	0.262537	-3.600094	0.0155
LNQUAPUB	2.450692	2.578227	0.950534	0.3855
LNQUAPUB (-1)	-4.284065	2.102188	-2.037907	0.0971
LNQUAPUB (-2)	-2.959598	1.565877	-1.890058	0.1174
LNQUAPUB (-3)	-5.300715	1.619146	-3.273772	0.0221
LNMAECON	-1.298178	1.862980	-0.696829	0.5170
LNMAECON (-1)	8.124249	3.395708	2.392505	0.0622
LNMAECON (-2)	-5.233418	2.450613	-2.135555	0.0858
LNCCTL	2.968447	4.895594	0.606351	0.5708
LNCCTL (-1)	4.778278	7.674424	0.622624	0.5608
LNCCTL (-2)	10.85593	7.048587	1.540158	0.1841
LNCCTL (-3)	18.10589	5.143718	3.520000	0.0169
LNBFMGT	-1.404180	2.069749	-0.678430	0.5276
LNBFMGT (-1)	-8.642226	3.732725	-2.315259	0.0685
LNBFMGT (-2)	4.947622	3.551343	1.393169	0.2223
C	3.707071	0.625690	5.924770	0.0020
R-squared	0.947385	Mean dependent var		0.559259
Adjusted R-squared	0.726400	S.D. dependent var		0.188637
S.E. of regression	0.098670	Akaike info criterion		-1.850837
Sum squared resid	0.048679	Schwarz criterion		-0.794969
Log likelihood	46.98629	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-1.536872
F-statistic	4.287099	Durbin-Watson stat		3.238031
Prob (F-statistic)	0.040525			

Igwemma Andrew A., Emerenini Fabian M., *Ogu Callistus., and Mbata Michael N.

*Note: p-values and any subsequent tests do not account for model selection.

From the ARDL result above;

LNQUAPUB: has a significant relationship with MILEXP at the 3rd lag; however, the relationship was insignificant at the current level, 1st and 2nd lag respectively at 5% level of significance.

LNMAECON: had an insignificant relationship with MILEXP from the current period through to the 2nd lag at 5% level of significance.

LNCCTL: had a significant relationship with MILEXP at the 3rd lag; however, the relationship was insignificant at the current level, 1st and 2nd lags respectively at 5% level of significance.

LNBFMGT: had an insignificant relationship with MILEXP from the current level, through to the 1 and 2nd lags respectively at 5% level of significance.

4.2.1: ARDL Cointegrating and Long Run Form

ARDL Cointegrating And Long Run Form

Dependent Variable: MILEXP

Selected Model: ARDL (7, 2, 3, 2, 3)

Date: 09/22/25 Time: 03:27

Sample: 1990 2023

Included observations: 27

Cointegrating Form

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D (MILEXP (-1))	4.169765	0.826814	5.043172	0.0040
D (MILEXP (-2))	3.458157	0.701925	4.926672	0.0044
D (MILEXP (-3))	2.959370	0.548355	5.396809	0.0029
D (MILEXP (-4))	2.308765	0.493883	4.674718	0.0055
D (MILEXP (-5))	1.583345	0.370197	4.277030	0.0079
D (MILEXP (-6))	0.945159	0.262537	3.600094	0.0155
D (LNMAECON)	-1.298178	1.862980	-0.696829	0.5170
D (LNMAECON (-1))	5.233418	2.450613	2.135555	0.0858
D (LNCCTL)	2.968447	4.895594	0.606351	0.5708
D (LNCCTL (-1))	-10.855934	7.048587	-1.540158	0.1841
D (LNCCTL (-2))	-18.105889	5.143718	-3.520000	0.0169
D (LNBFMGT)	-1.404180	2.069749	-0.678430	0.5276
D (LNBFMGT (-1))	-4.947622	3.551343	-1.393169	0.2223

Igwemma Andrew A., Emerenini Fabian M., *Ogu Callistus., and Mbata Michael N.

D (LNQUAPUB)	2.450692	2.578227	0.950534	0.3855
D (LNQUAPUB (-1))	2.959598	1.565877	1.890058	0.1174
D (LNQUAPUB (-2))	5.300715	1.619146	3.273772	0.0221
CointEq (-1)	-0.884759	0.998605	-5.892978	0.0020

$$\text{Cointeq} = \text{MILEXP} - (0.2706 * \text{LNMAECON} + 6.2379 \text{LNCCTL} - 0.8664$$

$$*\text{LNBFGMT} - 1.7152 * \text{LNQUAPUB} + 0.6299)$$

From the short run result above, it can be seen that CCTL, QUAPUB, BFMGT, MAECON were all insignificant at 5% level of significance. The ECM coefficient was negative and significant at

the 5% level of significance; hence, any short run dis-equilibrium in the model will be corrected at the rate of 88.4% per annum and this will take less than 2 years.

4.2.2: ARDL Long Run Form

Long Run Coefficients

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LNMAECON	0.270640	0.200445	1.350194	0.2349
LNCCTL	6.237902	1.307990	4.769073	0.0050
LNBFGMT	-0.866439	0.237612	-3.646451	0.0148
LNQUAPUB	-1.715225	0.345333	-4.966875	0.0042
C	0.629944	0.006137	102.646855	0.0000

Source: Author's Computation with E-views 9.

Long Run Analysis:

LNCCTL: has a negative and significant relationship with LNGDEBTGR at 5% level of significance. Hence; financial accountability has a significant impact on military expenditure in Nigeria in the long run.

LNQUAPUB: has a negative and significant relationship with MILEXP at 5% level of significance. Hence: good governance has a significant impact on military expenditure in Nigeria in the long run.

LNMAECON: has a positive and insignificant relationship with MILEXP at 5% level of

significance. Hence; Macro-economic environment has an insignificant impact on military spending in Nigeria in the long run.

LNBFGMT: has a negative and significant relationship with MILEXP at 5% level of significance. Hence: financial probity has a significant impact on military spending in Nigeria in the long run.

4.3 Test of Significance.

4.3.1 Individual Test of Significance.

1. CCTL

H₀: CCTL has no significant relationship with military expenditure in Nigeria at alpha = 0.05

Igwemma Andrew A., Emerenini Fabian M., *Ogu Callistus., and Mbata Michael N.

H₁: CCTL has a significant relationship with military expenditure in Nigeria at $\alpha = 0.05$
Prob. value = 0.0050 $\alpha = 0.05$

Decision: Since the prob.value (0.0050) < 0.05 the null hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that financial accountability has a significant relationship with military expenditure in Nigeria at $\alpha = 0.05$

ii. QUAPUB

Ho: QUAPUB has no significant relationship with military expenditure in Nigeria at $\alpha = 0.05$
H₁: QUAPUB has a significant relationship with military expenditure in Nigeria at $\alpha = 0.05$
Prob.value = 0.0042 $\alpha = 0.05$

Decision: Since the prob.value (0.0000) < 0.05 the null hypothesis rejected and it is concluded that good governance has a significant relationship with military expenditure in Nigeria at $\alpha = 0.05$

iii. BFMGT

Ho: BFMGT has no significant relationship with military spending in Nigeria at $\alpha = 0.05$
H₁: BFMGT has a significant relationship with military spending in Nigeria at $\alpha = 0.05$
Prob.value = 0.0148 $\alpha = 0.05$

Decision: Since the prob.value (0.0148) < 0.05 the null hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that financial probity has a significant relationship with military spending in Nigeria at $\alpha = 0.05$

ii. MAECON

Ho: MAECON has no significant relationship with military expenditure in Nigeria at $\alpha = 0.05$

HI: MAECON has a significant relationship with military expenditure in Nigeria at $\alpha = 0.05$
Prob.value = 0.2349 $\alpha = 0.05$

Decision: Since the prob.value (0.2349) > 0.05 the null hypothesis is accepted and it is concluded that the macro-economic environment has no significant relationship with military expenditure in Nigeria at $\alpha = 0.05$

4.3.2 Joint Test of Significance (ANOVA).

Ho: CCTL-MAECON=BFMGT-QUAPUB=0

H₁: CCTL/MAECON/BFMGT/QUAPUB/0

Decision: From the regression result, the F-prob. value is 0.040525 which is less than 0.05; hence we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a joint impact of CCTL, MAECON, BFMGT and QUAPUB on military expenditure in Nigeria at 5% level of significance.

4.4 Post Estimation Tests

4.4.1 Breusch-Godfrey

Serial

Correlation LM test.

Ho: There is no serial autocorrelation in the model at $\alpha = 0.05$.

H: There is presence of serial autocorrelation in the model at $\alpha = 0.05$.

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:

F-statistic	4.619964	Prob. F (1, 4)	0.0980
Obs R-squared	14.47095	Prob. Chi-Square (1)	0.0001

Decision: Since the observed Prob. Chi-square value is greater than 0.05, it means that there is no serial correlation in the model.

Ho: There is no heteroscedasticity in the model at a = 0.05.

H: There is presence of heteroscedasticity in the model at a = 0.05.

4.4.2 Breusch-Godfrey Test for Heteroscedasticity.

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

F-statistic	0.980616	Prob. F (21, 5)	0.5689
Obs R-squared	21, 72511	Prob. Chi-Square (21)	0.4155
Scaled explained SS	0.617958	Prob. Chi-Square (21)	1.0000

Decision: Since the Prob. Chi-square value (0.5689) is greater than 0.05, it means that there is no evidence of heteroscedasticity in the model.

between other control variables in the model (See appendix for table).

4.4.4 Goodness of Fit of the Model.

Adj.R2 0.726400 x 100% = 72.64%

From the result of the regression, the Adjusted R-squared shows that about 72.64% variation in military expenditure can be explained by the explanatory variables; hence, the model has a very strong explanatory power in relation to military expenditure in Nigeria.

4.4.3 Test for Causality

Ho: There is no causality between government debt growth rate and economic growth of Nigeria at $\alpha = 0.05$.

H1: There is causality between government debt growth rate and economic growth of Nigeria at $\alpha = 0.05$.

Decision: From the Granger causality test result, it was seen that causality exists and flowed unidirectionally from MAECON→BFMGT; BFMGTCCTL; QUAPUB→CCTL, QUAPUB→BFMGT. From the causality test, it can be seen that there is no direct causality between corruption and military expenditure, but

4.5 Discussion of Findings

CCTL was positively related to military expenditure and statistically significant at 5% level of significance in the long run. The positive relationship contravenes with our a priori expectation. The significant relationship it bears with military expenditure is suggestive of the fact that the effect of corruption erodes growth and development in the long run results

of previous studies of Duruji (2018); Suleiman and Aminu (2015); Akume and Godswill (2016); Usman (2017); Shimawua (2020), who all found that corruption has affected military expenditure in Nigeria. Based on the findings of these studies, this study corroborates that corruption has affected military expenditure in Nigeria.

MAECON was positively related to military expenditure and statistically insignificant at 5% level of significance in the long run. The positive relationship supports our a priori expectation as expected. The insignificant relationship it bears with economic growth is suggestive of the fact that the economic posture of the economy doesn't matter much as the fiscal needs can be augmented through outsourcing or borrowing; hence, the fiscal policy rating position is not a key factor when it comes to matters of security in the long run.

BFMGT was negatively related to military expenditure and statistically significant at 5% level of significance in the long run. The negative relationship contravenes with our a priori expectation. The result of the findings suggests that the role of budget management i.e. financial probity determines how far reaching military expenditure will produce the anticipated spending effects in the economy. However, in the case of Nigeria, military spending has been affected by economic mismanagement arising from budget manipulations such as inflation of the budget or what was once popularly known as budget padding by the legislature.

Igwemma Andrew A., Emerenini Fabian M., *Ogu Callistus., and Mbata Michael N.

QUAPUB was negatively related to military expenditure and statistically significant at 5% level of significance in the long run. The positive relationship contravenes with our a priori expectation. This research finding is supportive of the fact that the quality of public administration in Nigeria is rather poor as a result of poor governance. The significant relationship it bears with military expenditure leaves much to be desired in the long run as much is needed to be done to raise the index of good governance from its current rating to a higher one which should reflect rule of law, due process and democratic ideals that fight the growth of corruption of any form.

5.0 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of Findings

The study examined corruption on military expenditure in Nigeria for a 34-year period (1990-2023). The following summarizes the findings of the research;

- i. Corruption, good governance and financial probity have a significant effect on military expenditure in Nigeria;
 - ii. There is a joint impact of good governance, financial probity, macro-economic environment and corruption on military expenditure in Nigeria; and lastly
- There is no direct causality between corruption and military expenditure in Nigeria

5.2 Conclusion

The findings showed that corruption, good governance and financial probity had a

significant impact on military expenditure in Nigeria in the long run. Even though there was no direct causality between corruption and military expenditure in Nigeria, it was shown that the control variables—financial probity and good governance were significant in the outcome of the analysis; hence, further validating the joint test of significance. Based on evidence from the above findings, it was concluded that corruption has a significant impact on military expenditure in Nigeria.

5.3 Recommendations

From the findings of the study the following recommendations were made. They are as follows:

i. A major policy implication of this result is that concerted effort should be made by the government to curtail corrupt practices in governance. By so doing the country will save its financial resources and put it to best uses for developmental purposes such as maintaining law and order, national security etc.

ii. Again, the government should ensure probity in the use and management of its appropriation budget so as to ensure maximum compliance with its provision and follow due

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process in any procurement policy that enhances transparency and accountability.,

iii. Lastly, the government should enshrine and imbibe the tenets of good governance as it will produce a positive spill-over effect on budget management and impact on the economic environment in the long run.

5.4 Suggestions for Further Studies.

i. A VAR analysis will be adequate to capture the interaction between the variables when they are all transformed exogenously to become endogenous at some point. This will show greater interaction among the variables and their causality effects.

ii. An expansion of the variables and the use of Non-Linear auto-regressive distributed lag (NARDL) model analysis might produce more interesting results.

5.5 Contribution to Knowledge

The work has contributed to knowledge by modelling military expenditure as a function of corruption using an econometric approach to analysis as opposed to qualitative studies in previous studies. Furthermore, the study enlarged the scope of study to a current time period.

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